

Copper(II) Diamine Complex catalysed Hydrolysis of Diisopropyl-aminofluorophosphate

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Manuscript received 25 February 1992, revised 23 June 1992, accepted 16 July 1992

Kinetics of hydrolysis of diisopropylaminofluorophosphate (MIPAFOX) has been studied using copper(II) diamine complexes as catalyst. The pseudo-first order rate constants, activation energies and ΔS^\ddagger have been calculated. The high negative ΔS^\ddagger suggests complex formation between Cu^{II} complex and the substrate in the transition state.

The hydrolysis of highly toxic phosphorus esters has been a highly productive area of research during the last few decades. The use of metal ions and complexes in this field, though known for quite sometime, has achieved new dimensions in recent years. Most of the workers have made use of Cu, Co and Zn complexes for achieving the goals. Tetraza complexes of zinc were found to be very efficient for the hydrolysis of bis (*p*-nitrophenyl)phosphate¹. Co^{III} complexes of tri- and tetraamines were found to be very good catalysts for both good and poor leaving groups of phosphate esters². Cu^{II} ion catalysed³ and Cu^{II} montmorillonite catalysed⁴ hydrolysis of some pesticides have also been reported. In our earlier papers^{5,6} we have shown that copper(II) diamine complexes are the most effective catalysts for the hydrolysis of diisopropylfluorophosphate (DFP) and diethyl *p*-nitrophenylthionophosphate (parathion) which are di- and triphosphates respectively. In the present communication we report the extension of the work on copper(II) diamine catalysed hydrolysis to a phosphoramidate, diisopropylaminofluorophosphate (mipafox).

Results and Discussion

The concentration of the complex being in excess the reaction, follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The kinetic data on the hydrolysis of mipafox are given in Table 1. It is evident from the data that the k_{obs} values of TMEN complex of Cu^{II} perchlorate is maximum among the various catalysts used, indicating thereby its highest catalytic activity. These data also show that the activity of Cu^{II} nitrate-TMEN is almost negligible. The catalytic activity of TMEN complexes of Cu^{II} can be arranged in the following order on the basis of the results: Cu^{II} perchlorate > Cu^{II} trichloroacetate > Cu^{II} nitrate.

The catalytic activity of DAP complexes of these Cu^{II} salts are also in the same order but with insignificant variations. These differences were more pronounced in case of DFP⁵ and parathion⁶. The results of the hydrolysis of DFP, parathion and mipafox show that as the lewis acid character of the central metal atom increases, the catalytic activity also increases. The catalytic activity also changes with the basicity of the diamine ligands for a particular Cu^{II} salt. Thus

TABLE I—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE Cu^{II} DIAMINE COMPLEX CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF MIPAFOX

Compd.	$10^4(\text{complex})$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5(\text{mipafox})$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^{-3} E_a$ J mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
Cu^{II} perchlorate TMEN		30.0	183.0		
			37.5	200.0	
	25.0	62.5	183.0	43.9	-163
		100.0	180.0		
		125.0	178.0		
Cu^{II} trichloroacetate TMEN		37.5	75.0		
			50.0	74.0	
	25.0	62.5	75.0	41.8	-177
		100.0	75.0		
		125.0	74.0		
Cu^{II} perchlorate DAP		50.0	63.0		
			75.0	64.0	
	25.0	100.0	60.0	60.2	-118
		125.0	63.0		
Cu^{II} trichloroacetate DAP		50.0	65.0		
			75.0	66.0	
	25.0	100.0	66.0	53.5	-140
		125.0	66.7		
Cu^{II} nitrate TMEN	>25.0				No reaction or negligible

TMEN being the least basic in the order ethylene diamine > DAP > TMEN, gives the best catalytic activity which then falls with increasing basicity.

molecule and hydrolyses quickly. Complex formation between the Cu^{II} complex and mipafox is taken to be the rate-determining step (Scheme 1).

The rate of hydrolysis of mipafox is less than that of DFP with all the diamine complexes and k_{obs} is invariant with ionic strength. The complexes are also not active in non-aqueous solvents. These observations lend support to the fact that the mechanism of hydrolysis does not change with structural variations in the substrate molecule from DFP to mipafox. The rate retardation in case of mipafox, however, may be attributed to the attachment of more basic isopropylamino groups making the phosphorus atom more electron-rich and thereby decreasing its electrophilicity. As a consequence, pulling out of electrons from P—F bond becomes difficult in the transition state resulting in the retardation of the rate of hydrolysis. Alternatively, the nitrogen atoms of mipafox may coordinate with the central metal atom thereby hindering the formation of aquo complex and retarding the rate of hydrolysis.

The higher value of activation energy as compared to DFP again supports low catalytic activity for mipafox. The high ΔS^\ddagger values for all the complexes with mipafox and the non-variance of k_{obs} values with the change in ionic strength support that the reaction is non-ionic and associative type.

Based on our experimental findings, the most probable mechanism for the hydrolysis of mipafox could be the initial aquo-complex formation followed by a transition complex formation with the substrate. The water molecules bound to the central metal atom attack the bound substrate

Experimental

The complexes CuX₂L₂ (where X = ClO₄⁻, CCl₃COO⁻, NO₃⁻; L = *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine, TMEN and 1,3-diaminopropane (DAP) were prepared and characterised by the reported method⁵. Mipafox was prepared by standard method⁷ and its purity checked by glc. The conductivity was measured using a Apx-185 conductivity meter and the cell was kept in a Julabo F-50 Ultratemp 2000 thermostat; the temperature range selected was 27–50°. The hydrolysis of mipafox was followed by measuring the change in conductivity of liberated HF in unbuffered aqueous solution. The reaction kinetics were followed under pseudo-first order conditions. Kinetic run was always carried out in duplicate and gave rate constants with an uncertainty of less than ±5%.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. R. V. Swamy, Director for his encouragement and Mr. Mitthan Lal for secretarial assistance.

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